

The comparative studies of micellization and electrolytic behaviour of dysprosium soaps in methanol

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Abstract : Dysprosium butyrate, valerate, myristate and stearate behave as weak electrolyte in dilute solutions. The critical micelle concentrations (CMC) of dysprosium soaps in methanol have been determined by conductometric measurement. The value of CMC decreases with increasing chain length of fatty acid component. The molar conductances at infinite dilution and degree of ionization have been evaluated.

Keywords : Dysprosium soaps, weak electrolyte, conductivity, critical micelle concentration.

Introduction

The metallic soaps are being widely used in many industries and so the information on their structure and nature are of great importance for their use in industries and for explaining their characteristics under different conditions. The present work deals with the determination of the critical micelle concentration, degree of dissociation and dissociation constant of dysprosium soaps by conductometric measurement of the solutions in methanol¹. With the help of dissociation equilibria of dysprosium soaps in non aqueous solvent gives us information regarding the nature of soap in solution. They behave as weak electrolyte below the CMC.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H./A.R. grade. Solvent methanol was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Dysprosium soap (butyrate, valerate, myristate and stearate) were synthesised as mentioned in our earlier communication². The metal soaps thus obtained were recrystallized twice from methanol and dried under vacuum for at least 48 h before use.

The conductance of soap solutions in methanol was measured with digital conductivity meter (Toshniwal CL 01.10 A) and dipping type conductivity cell with platinised electrodes (cell constant 0.875) at 40 ± 0.05 °C in a thermostat.

Results and discussion

The specific conductance, k of the solution of dysprosium soaps (butyrate, valerate, myristate and stearate) in methanol increases with increasing concentration and decreasing chain length of the soap. The increase in the specific conductance may be due to the fact dysprosium soaps behave as simple electrolytes in dilute solutions and are ionized into simple metal cations, Dy^{3+} and fatty acid anions, $RCOO^-$ (where R is C_3H_7 , C_4H_9 , $C_{13}H_{27}$ and $C_{17}H_{35}$ for butyrate, valerate, myristate and stearate). The decrease in specific conductance with increasing chainlength of the soap may be due to increasing size and decreasing mobility of anions in the soap molecule. It may be pointed out that the micellization process in organic solvents is somewhat different from that in aqueous solutions. The aggregation begins at very low concentration in organic solvent and results in the formation of very much smaller aggregate.

The main cause of micellization in organic solvent is the energy change due to dipole-dipole interaction between the polar head groups of soap molecules.

The plots of specific conductance vs soap concentration in methanol are characterized by intersection of two straight lines at definite soap concentrations, 0.0018, 0.0021, 0.0047 and 0.0045 mol dm⁻¹, stearate, respectively, molar conductance 3.13, 2.96, 1.11 and 2.65 mho cm mol⁻¹; K , 0.35×10^5 , 0.94×10^5 , 11.8×10^7 and 2.4×10^7 respectively corresponding to the CMC of

Fig. 1(a). Molar conductance vs square root of concentration of dysprosium soaps in methanol.

dysprosium butyrate, valerate, myristate and stearate, respectively.

It is suggested that the soap is considerably ionized in dilute solutions and anions begin to aggregate to form ionic micelles at CMC.

The result shows that CMC decrease with increasing chain length of the soap molecule.

Fig. 1(b). $\mu^3 C^3$ vs $1/\mu$ of dysprosium soaps in methanol.

The molar conductance, μ of the solutions of dysprosium soaps in methanol decreases with increasing concentration and chain length of the soap.

The decrease may be attributed to the combined effects of the ionic atmosphere, solvation of ions, decrease of mobility and formation of micelles. The plots of molar conductance μ vs square root of soap concentration $C^{1/2}$ (Fig. 1(a)) are concave upwards, indicating that the soaps behave as weak electrolytes in dilute solutions. The limiting molar conductance μ_0 of these soap solutions cannot be

obtained by the usual extrapolation method and the Debye-Hückel-Onsager equation is not applicable to these soap solutions in methanol. The soaps in dilute solutions behave as weak electrolytes and so an expression for the ionization of dysprosium soaps can be developed using the Ostwald model. If C is the concentration in mol/L and α is the degree of ionization of the soaps, the equivalent concentration of different species can be represented as

where $R = \text{C}_3\text{H}_7$, C_4H_9 , $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{27}$ and $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35}$ for valerate, butyrate, myristate and stearate, respectively.

The ionization constant, K can be expressed as :

$$K = 27C^3\alpha^4 / (1 - \alpha) \quad (1)$$

Since the number of ions for a weak electrolyte in dilute solutions is relatively small and interionic effects are almost negligible, the activities of ions may be taken as proportional to the concentration and the conductance ratio (Arrhenius dissociation), μ/μ_0 , is reasonably good measure for the degree of ionization α (where μ is the molar conductance at finite concentration and μ_0 is the molar conductance at infinite dilution). On substituting the value of α and rearranging eq. (1), one obtains

$$\mu^3 C^3 = \frac{K\mu_0^4}{27\mu} - \frac{K\mu_0^3}{27} \quad (2)$$

The values of the ionization constant, K , and μ_0 can be obtained from the slope ($K\mu_0^4/27$) and intercept ($-K\mu_0^3/27$) of the linear portion of the plots of $\mu^3 C^3$ vs $1/\mu$ (Fig. 1(b)) for dilute soap solutions. The values of the degree of ionization α at different soap concentrations have been calculated by assuming that it is equal to the conductance ratio, μ/μ_0 . The low values of the degree of ionization α show that the solutions of dysprosium soaps in methanol behave as weak electrolytes. The degree of ionization decreases rapidly in dilute solutions with increasing soap

concentration whereas the values of α decrease slowly above the CMC. The values of the ionization constant, K have been calculated by using eq. (1) and assuming the degree of ionization as equal to the conductance ratio. The values of K remain nearly constant with increase in the soap concentration below the CMC, as expected for weak electrolytes, but increase above the CMC. The increase in the values of ionization constant above the CMC may be partly due to the fact that the conductance ratio (μ/μ_0) is not exactly equal to the degree of ionization, α but mainly due to the fact that activity co-efficient of ions are not exactly equal to unity. The deviations observed at higher soap concentrations in methanol from the Debye-Hückel treatment are in agreement with the Bjerrum and Fuoss and Kraus extensions of the Debye-Hückel theory.

The results show that the soaps behave as weak electrolytes in dilute solutions below the CMC and the conductance results can be explained on the basis of Debye-Hückel theory and the Ostwald's formula of weak electrolytes.

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